

COVID-19 AND MACROECONOMIC ASPECTS: EFFECT ON INDIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract

The present study examines the impact of COVID-19 on the Indian economy from various viewpoints such as growth, employment, trade, and others. This paper highlights the fallout on the Indian economy due to the measures and policy initiatives taken by authorities to curb the pandemic and its impact on various economic sectors. These economic impacts have added to the already deteriorating consumption and demand situation in the country. A recession is expected to hit the world economy, and India is no exception. The present study suggests various measures to respond to the challenges posed through quantitative and qualitative measures for the economic revival of India.

Keywords: COVID-19, India, Unemployment, Trade, Economic growth

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has not only taken a toll on the lives of humans but also brought to a standstill the social and economic lives of people around the world. The pandemic is expected to have long-term economic impacts because of the disruption to the global supply chain and trade restrictions. Every sector has witnessed a negative impact of the pandemic, be it primary, secondary, or tertiary (Whiting, 2020). A contraction of 5.2 per cent was expected in the global GDP in 2020, along with induction of deep recession, lower level of investment, and loss of education and work (The World Bank, 2020b). Table 1 shows the macroeconomic impacts of a reduction in global economic growth by one per cent based on factors like real GDP, household real consumption and exports.

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Table I: Macroeconomic Impacts of One Per Cent Reduction in Global Economic Growth

		Labour Productivity Scenario	Total Productivity Scenario	Trade Costs Scenario
Base Value bn USD 2011	Per Cent Change			
Real GDP				
World	111,387	-1.0	-1.0	-1.0
Developed Countries	66,362	-1.0	-1.0	-0.7
Developing Countries	45,024	-1.0	-1.0	-1.5
Household Real Consumption				
World	46,746	-1.1	-1.0	-0.9
Developed Countries	30,268	-1.2	-1.0	-0.7
Developing Countries	16,477	-1.0	-1.0	-1.4
Exports, Constant Dollars				
World	17,849	-1.1	-1.0	-13.8
Developed Countries	9,524	-1.1	-1.0	-124
Developing Countries	8,325	-1.1	-1.0	-15.4

Source: IFPRI (2011)

The COVID-19 virus has impacted economies around the world. These unprecedented disruptions in economic activities caused by the pandemic have also been observed in India. It has acutely affected trade, global value chains, medium and small enterprises, and networks of domestic production, leading to a decline in overall welfare and economic growth (Jaramillo, 2020). Many studies have compared the economic shock of the pandemic to the financial crises of 2008–09. Both crises are similar in some aspects (like intervention by the government through fiscal and monetary policies to provide temporary support to the downfall). The restrictions imposed during the pandemic in the form of complete and partial lockdowns affected various sectors in a significant way. Affected industries include tourism, hotels, manufacturing, restaurants, non-essential retail trade, etc. (WTO, 2020). The economic shocks that emerged due to the pandemic are mainly in the form of total factor productivity, trade and labour productivity shocks (Vos et al., 2020).

In September 2020, India took over Brazil with more than 4.2 million confirmed infection cases and reached second place in the world. Not only from a health point of view, but the pandemic also affected India economically

and socially (WHO, 2020a). The lockdown imposed by the Indian government slowed down the supply-side of a developing economy that was going through a state of demand depression and a high level of unemployment (Singh, 2020). According to an estimate by the Asian Development Bank, the outbreak of COVID-19 was estimated to cost the Indian economy a personal consumption loss between the US\$ 387 million and US \$29.9 billion (FICCI, 2020).

Mishra (2019) found that the growth model of India depends on export-led growth. COVID-19 is expected to have an impact on areas like financial markets, growth, poverty and international trade. From the trade perspective, a downfall of 13–32 per cent is expected under optimistic and pessimistic scenarios, respectively. Jaffrelot (2020) found that the economic slowdown already existed in India before the outbreak of the COVID-19, the reason for the same was not the limited integration into the global economy of India, but it was the result of the growth without development kind of imbalances which are already prevailing for years in the Indian economy. Sahoo and Ashwani (2020) analyse the impact of COVID-19 on growth, trade, the MSME sector and manufacturing in India. The study found that under optimistic and pessimistic scenarios, there is a possibility of negative growth between 3 and 7 per cent; for manufacturing, the downfall expected is 5.5–20 per cent; for exports it is 13.7–20.8 per cent; for imports between 17.3 and 20 per cent; and for MSME from 2.1 to 5.7 per cent. It suggests that there is a need for measures in terms of fiscal-monetary stimulus. Jakhotiya (2020) found that already existing cyclical and structural flaws were brought out by COVID-19. In India, the already prevailing structural flaws that were not cured by economic reforms such as crony capitalism, growing unemployment, systematic corruption, banking sector inefficiency, illiteracy and rural economy stagnation came out widely because of the COVID-19 effect.

Patnaik and Sengupta (2020) found a baseline fiscal deficit of 6.2 per cent for the central government in 2020–21 with the assumption of 5 per cent decrease in real GDP. Moreover, an increase in the fiscal deficit beyond the levels would be there if government spending increases beyond the level. Maliszewska, et. al. (2020) suggested that Internet devices, sensors and mobile devices can be used to track and monitor the travel history of people, and this can be used to overcome the adverse effect of COVID-19 on the socio-economic aspects of the Indian economy. The study also provided an insight into the effects of the pandemic on different sectors and emphasised the role of top-level management in private and government sectors in strategic decision-making. Chabria (2020) suggested that the measures taken by the central banks of India to revive the economy had some limitations. Since the economy is facing an increasing rate of inflation, policy rates needed to be slashed. In addition to this, the debt–GDP ratio is also increasing along with

the demand for increasing yields on government bonds by investors. The report suggested that to effectively maintain liquidity flow in the economy, the Reserve Bank of India should bring out a resolution and think of a way to monetise the government's debt.

In light of the above discussion, the present study tries to examine the economic impact of COVID-19 in India, based on various aspects such as economic growth, trade, level of employment and sectoral impact. Further, it studies various measures adopted by the government and their probable impacts.

Impact of COVID-19 on the Indian Economy

The COVID-19 crisis has affected the core of economies across the world, including those of South Asian countries. Figure 1 shows the risks faced by the South Asian economies in terms of their expected GDP contraction because of the coronavirus. Among the countries in South Asia, India has had the second-highest number of infection cases, which impacted socio-economic sectors of the country (WHO, 2020b).

COVID-19 has impacted all sectors in India and not just the health sector, owing to its weak healthcare infrastructure. Both the supply and demand sides were affected simultaneously (Subramanian, 2021). According to Oxford Economics, through the middle of the decade, the production and manufacturing output will be 12 per cent below the pre-virus levels even if the pandemic situation is over. A detailed analysis of the impact of the virus on various parts of the Indian economy has been presented in the following sections of the paper.

Figure 1: Risks Associated with COVID-19 in South Asia

Source: World Bank (2020)

Impact on Economic Growth

In the first quarter of the financial year 2020–21, the Indian economy witnessed a contraction of about 24 per cent and in the second quarter of around 7.5 per cent (Mishra, 2020). Figure 2 shows India's GDP growth rate after the outbreak of the pandemic. Since the first quarter of 2020, the growth rate started declining and even became negative in the first quarter of 2021. However, the fall in the second quarter of 2021 is less than the first one.

Figure 2: India's GDP Growth Rate After the Outbreak of COVID-19

Source: Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (2020)

According to the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (2020), in comparison with the real GDP of ₹145.66 lakh crore in 2019–20, the real GDP is at ₹134.40 lakh crore in 2020–21. The bottom 30–40 per cent of individuals and enterprises were mostly affected due to the huge cost-cutting measures taken by large Indian firms.

Impact on Employment Levels

According to the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy, as of November 2020, India's labour force participation rate was 39.3 per cent, the unemployment rate was 7.8 per cent and the employment rate was 36.24 per cent. Figure 3 shows the unemployment rate since the outbreak of the pandemic. The unemployment rate was at its peak in April and May 2020. The rate of urban unemployment was higher than the rate of unemployment in rural India. The unemployment rate started falling again and continued until November 2020; after that, a rise was witnessed in December 2020.

Table 3 shows the state-wise unemployment rate in India in December 2020. Haryana has the highest unemployment rate of 32.5 per cent followed by Rajasthan, Tripura, Jammu & Kashmir, Uttar Pradesh, and so on. In addition to this, a large number of migrant workers become unemployed, particularly semi and unskilled workers, who had to return to their hometowns due to the lockdown (Berkel, 2020).

Figure 3: Unemployment Levels After the Outbreak of the COVID-19 Pandemic

Source: CMIE Database

Table 2: States with Highest Unemployment Rate in India (December 2020)

State	Unemployment Rate
Haryana	32.5
Rajasthan	28.2
Tripura	18.2
Jammu & Kashmir	16.6
Uttar Pradesh	14.9
Goa	13.2
Bihar	12.7
Jharkhand	12.4

Source: CMIE Database

Impact on Trade

Close interdependence among economies can bring a plethora of opportunities. It can, however, also carry with it a risk, as was made clear during the COVID-19 pandemic. The development of a nation in a globalised world is often determined by its level of world trade and investment. The pandemic had a great impact on trade and investment worldwide by creating a huge disruption in demand as well as supply (WTO, 2020). According to a report by UNCTAD (2020b), there would be a US\$50 billion decrease in the

world export level because of the disruptions created by the pandemic. India is no exception, and it is among the top 15 countries most affected by trade disruptions. The impact of the coronavirus is expected to be around US\$ 348 million. Additionally, the merchandise export decreased 4.78 per cent to reach US\$ 314.31 billion in the financial year 2020.

Impact on Different Sectors

All sectors have seen the impact of COVID-19 in India (Figure 4). The agriculture sector has seen a decline of 3.36 per cent, the manufacturing sector of 3.98 per cent, and the services sector of 4.35 per cent. It is generally observed that the least sharp fluctuations are seen in the services sector. However, the COVID-19 pandemic badly hit the services sector. The agriculture and services sector was affected indirectly because some services like transportation, retail and wholesale services play a mediating role between the producers and the consumers. Personal services—maids, health, barbers and others—were also got affected because of the pandemic (UNCTAD, 2020a).

Additionally, natural resources suffered a loss of 0.8 per cent and trade tourist services of 8.76 per cent (Mahapatra, 2020; Maliszewska et al., 2020). Food security was also affected by the pandemic, and it can be seen in the form of disrupted supply chains, loss of income, remittances and an increase in food price inflation. According to the UN World Food Programme, there were around 135 million people facing food insecurity before the pandemic; this number has almost doubled with an increase of around 130 million people who are now facing acute levels of food insecurity post-pandemic (World Bank, 2020a). Initially in India, the availability of food grains was not affected as there were sufficient buffers of food grains (58.4 million tons) and pulses (3 million tons); however, disruption of the supply chains has severely affected 78 per cent of short shelf-life food items like milk, vegetables, fruits, eggs, sugar and meat (Narayanan, 2020). The loss has impacted all parts of the demand and supply chain including consumers, farmers and traders.

According to the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India, the growth percentage of the agriculture and mining sectors has fallen from 4 per cent and 3.1 per cent, respectively, in 2019–2020 to 3.4 per cent and -12.4 per cent in 2020–21. Figure 3 shows the impact of COVID-19 on various sectors like agriculture, manufacturing, finance, real estate and others. The worst affected in the first quarter were construction and manufacturing. The lockdown has put a lot of pressure on the manufacturing sector, which was contributing around 20 per cent to India's GDP. The auto industry is one of the important sub-sector of manufacturing, with a share of around 50 per cent.

Figure 4: Impact on Various Sectors' GDP of COVID-19

Source: Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India

Table 3 shows the comparison of Gross Value Added (GVA) of various sectors in India in the first quarter of 2020 with the first quarter of 2021. Except for the agriculture and allied sector, the other sectors saw a decrease in terms of GVA. Seasonal factors also played a significant role in the less impact of COVID-19 on the agriculture and tourism sectors.

The situation is much worse for the unorganised sector as it is struggling to survive due to its lower profitability and retentive power (Jayaraman, 2020). Medium and small enterprises also witnessed a disruption of the international supply chain leading to a decline in their business. Further, a fall in the Goods and Services Tax collection of 41 per cent has been recorded in 2020, reflecting a slump in services and industrial production (Berkel, 2020). In addition to that, the aviation sector was also massively affected by COVID-19, as both domestic and international flights were stopped initially and then started with limited capacity, leading to losses faced by major airlines; for instance, Spice Jet and IndiGo showed a loss of 112 crores and 1,194 crores in the second quarter of 2020, along with job losses, salary cuts and leave without pay for employees (Business Insider India, 2020). The life and non-life insurance sector also faced a downfall of around 30 per cent and 15 per cent respectively, while the closure of businesses due to the lockdown affected general insurance (Sanghvi, 2021).

Table 3: Gross Value Added of Various Sectors in India

GVA at Basic Prices	2019–20		2020–21		Increase/Decrease
	Q1 (2019–20)	Share in Total GVA (%)	Q1 (2020–21)	Share in Total GVA (%)	
Agriculture, forestry and fishing	4,39,842.6	13.3	4,54,657.9	17.8	Increase
Mining and quarrying	92,806.5	2.8	71,208.9	2.8	Decrease
Manufacturing	5,78,936.5	17.5	3,51,395.6	13.8	Decrease
Electricity, gas, water supply and other utility services	81,627.9	2.5	75,876.7	3.0	Decrease
Construction	262,827.8	7.9	1,30,749.6	5.1	Decrease
Trade, hotels, transport, communication and services related to broadcasting	630,860.5	19.1	3,34,284.4	13.1	Decrease
Financial, real estate and professional services	8,03,322.2	24.3	760,490.9	29.8	Decrease
Public administration, defence and other services	4,17,483	12.6	3,74,656.2	14.7	Decrease
GVA at Basic Price	3,307,707	100	25,53,320	100	Decrease

Note: GVA – Gross Value Added

Source: Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India

Revival of the Economy: Current and Expected Policy Efforts

To pull out the economy from the worst of the pandemic, the government initiated fiscal measures with a relief package, under the name Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan, worth ₹20 lakh crore. The relief package consists of several schemes promoting the concept of ‘Make in India’ through increasing the use of domestic goods. To restart the operations, ₹3 lakh crore collateral-free loans to medium and small enterprises were announced. Additionally, in the first quarter of the present year, the Ministry of Finance relaxed the curbs imposed on 80 government departments to preserve cash. The government spending of the budget also increased by 12.7 per cent in 2020–21 (ASSOCHAM, 2020). However, under the Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Yojana of the government consisting of a direct benefit transfer of ₹1.7 lakh

crore, only ₹73,000 crores were the incremental amount, and the rest was already budgeted earlier in the year. The aspect to be made clear here is that the amount sanctioned under this scheme is only around one-third of the country's total migrant workers (Manikandan, 2020).

The important sectors that can revive the Indian economy are trade, transport, manufacturing, construction, broadcasting services and hotels. Some developments are being noticed in the agriculture and manufacturing sectors too (Mukhopadhyay, 2021). These changes began as early as 2020, as the manufacturing component of the Industrial Index of Production was at 129.8, and the agriculture contribution to GVA had increased. Along with this, the index for eight core industries was 131.9.

Production of tobacco products showed a growth rate of 2.9 per cent, intermediate goods 8.8 per cent, production of basic metals at 10.8 per cent, and food products at 2.7 per cent. According to the IHS Markit India Manufacturing Purchasing Managers Index (2020), the manufacturing sector also witnessed an increase from 56.8 in September 2020 to 58.9 in October 2020. Furthermore, based on the observations of the monetary policy committee of the Reserve bank of India, it was observed that the monetary, fiscal and sectoral policies hold a significant place to nurture the recovery and to achieve this; the policy repo rate, marginal standing facility and bank rate remained unchanged (Reserve Bank of India, 2021).

For the economic revival of countries, both private and public investments along with improvement in healthcare facilities are the need of the hour. However, in comparison to private investment, public investment can come to the rescue, as it is required to crowd in private investment. There is a lack of appropriate infrastructure facilities in India leading to a major hindrance in its growth, recovery and failure of industry, mainly the manufacturing sector (Ari and Koc, 2020). So, to boost the investors' confidence in the present pandemic situation, infrastructure facilities should be improved through public investment.

In addition to this, social security measures, specifically for the informal sector—around 90 per cent workforce of India is employed in the informal sector—are needed in India to control increasing levels of unemployment (Srivastava, 2020). Loss of jobs has also emerged as one of the major issues faced by the Indian economy. To counter it the government should consider providing incentives to employers so they can be retained. Further, to improve the demand and supply conditions, aggressive fiscal and monetary measures are required with a realistic perspective of restoring medium-term sustainability.

Conclusion

The Indian economy has a population of around 1.3 billion, and the initiatives taken by the government to combat the effects of the pandemic on such a huge population are less effective due to limited expenditures on public health, infrastructure and financial systems. The steps taken to curb the spread of the pandemic in India came in the form of a shutdown of various economic activities, such as trade, production and consumption, leading to market shock, supply shock, and demand shock, which will ultimately increase the chances of a global recession in the coming years. Though the Indian government took various measures to respond to the challenges posed, there is still a need to increase efforts, both quantitatively and qualitatively, to revive the economy. Marginalised communities, unorganised sectors, migrants and a few other sectors need most of the quantitative support from the authorities and qualitative measures that are self-reliant and sustainable developmental models with an environment-friendly inclusive framework.

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